

INTERFACIAL STUDIES ON ARAMID/EPOXY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

A Kevlar 49 fibre was subjected to cyclic deformation in the air and its mechanical deformation was monitored by Raman spectroscopy. Interfacial studies were conducted on a model composite consisting of a single Kevlar 49 fibre embedded in a Ciba-Geigy 1927 resin. The variation of strain along the fibre, as well as, the transfer lengths for reinforcement have been measured at various levels of applied load. Interfacial Shear Stress values were obtained by means of an analytical model consisting of an isolated fibre in an unbound matrix.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most frequently used experiments for measuring the interfacial shear strength (ISS) between fibre and matrix is the fragmentation test derived originally by Kelly¹. This test requires matrix strains of at least three to four times greater than the fibre strain to failure² and, therefore, is not suitable for polymer fibres such as Kevlar, PBT etc. with fracture strains in excess of 2%. In addition to that, polymer fibres fracture by axial splitting rather than transverse cracking, henceforth, crack location is hard to observe³.

In this work Laser Raman Spectroscopy (LRS) has been used to monitor the micromechanics of reinforcement in short Kevlar 49/ epoxy model systems and, in particular, (a) to obtain the load transfer profiles at each level of matrix strain, (b) to measure the transfer lengths for reinforcement at each level of applied load (c) to determine the effect of fibre-end geometry upon load transfer and (d) to measure the ISS using existing analytical models. This technique has already been applied successfully to follow the micromechanics of reinforcement⁴, as well as, the effect of resin shrinkage⁵ in polydiacetylene/ epoxy systems. In addition to that LRS has been used similarly to map out strains on aramid fibres in a unidirectional composite⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Sample preparation

Short, as received, Kevlar 49 fibres, 12 μ m in diameter were "chopped" from a continuous filament using (a) ceramic scissors and (b) a laser microprobe. Two different end-geometries were obtained on the same fibre; a blunt end from cutting with scissors and a round, slightly tapered end from cutting with the laser beam. In Table 1 the material properties are listed.

Table 1-Materials properties

Property	Ciba-Geigy 1927	Kevlar 49
E(GPa)	2.5	124
G _m (GPa)	0.92	-
ν	0.37	0.33 ¹⁰

Single filaments, approximately 1.7 mm in length, were embedded in a Ciba-Geigy HY/LY 1927 two-part solvent-free epoxy resin, using 100 parts (by weight) of resin to 36 parts of hardener. Dog-boned PTFE moulds were half filled with the resin/ hardener mixture and allowed to set partially before the fibre and the rest of the epoxy were added. The dogboned specimens were cured for 7 days at room temperature to avoid thermal stresses developing on the fibres due to matrix shrinkage. Strain gauges of gauge factor 2.1 were mounted on the flat surface of the specimen prior to testing. A small tensile loading device was used to apply stress on the kevlar 49/ Epoxy sample in the fibre direction. The device was mounted on a micrometer slide so that the whole length of the specimen could be transversed through the incident laser beam.

2. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra were taken employing the 632.8 nm line of a He-Ne laser. A 10X microscope objective was used to focus the incident light to a 8µm spot on the embedded fibre. The intensity of the light was kept below 8mW on the sample to avoid damaging the fibre or the resin. The 180 backscattered light was collected by the microscope objective and focused on the entrance slit of a SPEX double monochromator. A cooled CCD imaging detector was employed for recording the Raman spectra. All Raman experiments were concentrated on the 1615 cm⁻¹ band which shows the highest frequency shift with strain⁶.

A single filament in the air was recycled three times to 2% tensile strain while Raman spectra were taken at all different levels of its cyclic deformation. The kevlar 49/ Epoxy model composite was loaded twice to 1.5% on the tensometer described above while Raman spectra were taken point-by-point along the length of the fibre and at all different levels of matrix strain.

Fig.1 Raman Frequency as a function of Strain for the 1615 cm⁻¹ band of a kevlar 49 fibre:(a) 1st (b) 2nd and (c) 3rd loading/ unloading cycles.

RESULTS/ DISCUSSION

1. Single Filament in the Air

In Figs.1a, b and c the Raman frequency is plotted as a function of macroscopic strain in tension for the first, second and third cycles respectively. It can be seen that on loading there is a definite linear relationship between frequency and strain while on unloading curves of different slopes are obtained. It has already been reported elsewhere⁷ that there are two mechanisms contributing to the elastic extension of aramid fibres; a crystallite stretching parallel to the chains and a crystallite rotation due to a shearing deformation. The rotation comprises of a reversible and an irreversible component with the latter being responsible for the residual strain observed on unloading an unbroken fibre. However, Raman spectroscopy can only measure the extensional or chain stretching component of the strain in aramid fibres⁷. The linearity of the frequency versus strain relationship in tension (Figures 1a,b,c) indicates that each increment of overall fibre strain contributes to both extension and rotation of the crystallites all the way up to fracture. The percentage of overall strain that each component-extensional or rotational - carries depends on the crystallinity of the aramid fibre and, hence, its modulus⁷. On unloading, however, that percentage has been greatly affected in favour of the extensional element since the rotational contribution has now been reduced by the amount of irreversible deformation (Fig.1a). The deviation from linearity on unloading indicates that the overall strain is now distributed unevenly between the two components. During the second and third loading cycles (Fig.1b and b) a hysteresis is initially observed due to the residual strain in the fibre. The frequency versus strain slopes are now higher in value (Table 2) indicating that the material has now become stiffer. The slight drop of the slope at the third cycle is not significant as it lies within the experimental error. The Raman data therefore confirm the strain hardening or "conditioning" effect observed in aramid fibres upon recycling⁸.

Table 2-Strain Dependence of Vibrational Modes in Tension

Loading Cycle	Strain Dependence	Standard Deviation
1st	- 4.37	± 0.10
2nd	- 4.48	± 0.18
3rd	- 4.42	± 0.13

2. Model Composite

Fig. 2 shows the variation of fibre strain along the whole length of the embedded fibre for matrix strains of (a) 0.5% and 1.0%, first loading cycle and (b) 1.5%, second loading cycle, respectively. The profile corresponds broadly to the Cox or shear lag model⁹ whereby the load is built up from the fibre ends and becomes maximum at the middle. The load transfer profiles from the "scissors" and "laser" cut ends appear to be similar. Although the transmission of load from the ends of the fibre was difficult to monitor due to the damage caused by the cutting procedure, there is a definite indication that some load is transferred from the "scissors-cut" end due to matrix adhesion. Raman spectra could not be recorded from a region of about 20 μ m from the "laser-cut" end due to laser induced damage and the strain transfer profile appears truncated at that level (Fig. 2).

The fibre length over which the load is built up from each end of the fibre is defined, here, as the transfer length, l_t . Since the exact value of l_t is difficult to measure due to the parabolic shape of the load transfer profiles (Fig. 2) the value of $0.95 l_t$ was obtained instead. The values of $0.95 l_t$ as a function of matrix strain are given in Fig. 3 for both loading cycles. The data from both first and second loading cycles show a dramatic increase of transfer length up to about 1% strain followed by a plateau. It is interesting to note that shear lag type of analyses⁹ predict a constant transfer length with applied strain and, therefore, is not yet quite clear whether the observed situation is attributed to differential Poisson's contraction effects confined or to other causes.

Fig.2. Fibre Strain as a function of Fibre Length for (a) 1st cycle at 0.5% and 1.0% matrix strain and (b) second cycle at 1.5% matrix strain.

Kevlar 49/Epoxy

Fig.3 $95\% l_t$ versus Matrix Strain for both 1st and 2nd loading cycles.

INTERFACIAL MODELLING

Shear-lag analytical models are not applicable in single fibre composites since volume fraction is an input parameter. The only existing model on a single fibre surrounded by an unbound matrix is by Whitney and Drzal¹⁰. The model is based on classical theory of elasticity and predicts the stresses in the vicinity of a broken continuous fibre. The fibre axial normal stress, σ_x , on the fibre is given by:

$$\sigma_x = \{ 1 - [4.75 (x/L_c) + 1] e^{-4.75(x/L_c)} \} A_1 \epsilon_0 \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the far field axial strain, L_c is the critical length for the axial stress to recover 95% of its value from the broken end of a fibre. The interfacial shear stress τ_{xr} is given by:

$$\tau_{xr}(x/L_c, R) = -4.75 \mu A_1 \epsilon_0 (x/L_c) e^{-4.75 (x/L_c)} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mu = \left(\frac{G_m}{E_{1f} - 4\nu_{12f}G_m} \right)^{1/2}$$

G_m matrix shear modulus, E_{1f} the fibre axial modulus, ν_{12f} fibre's Poisson ratio. The following modifications were performed on Whitney and Drzal's model:

(a) The value of $L_c = 2 f(l_t)$,

where $f(l_t)$ is a function of the experimentally measured l_t with overall strain ϵ_0 and is defined, again, as the length required for the strain to recover 95% of its far field value.

(b) The stress is transferred from the ends of the short fibre.

(c) The parameter A_1 is assumed to be equal to E_{1f} since no thermal stresses are present and therefore σ_x/E_{1f} represents the axial strain in the fibre.

The equation (1) then becomes :

$$\epsilon_x/\epsilon_0 \approx 1 - [4.75x/ f(l_t) + 1] e^{-4.75x/ f(l_t)} \quad (3)$$

and, accordingly, equation (2) changes to :

$$\tau_{xr} \approx -4.75 \mu E_{1f} \epsilon_0 x/ f(l_t) e^{-4.75x/ f(l_t)} \quad (4)$$

where G_m the shear modulus of the matrix, and E_{1f} , ν_{12f} the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the fibre respectively (Table 1).

Fig. 4 Fibre Strain normalised to 1.5% Matrix Strain (1st loading cycle) as a function of Length normalised to 95% l_t . The solid lines represent equations (3).

The theoretical lines obtained from equation (3) together with the experimental data are plotted in Fig. 4 for 1.5% matrix strain (1st cycle) and, as can be seen, satisfactory fits are obtained. In Fig.5 the corresponding variation of interfacial shear stress is given as a function of normalised length. It can be seen that the system can sustain a maximum shear stress of about 55 MPa without any signs of interfacial failure. This value is in agreement with interlaminar shear strengths values of 48-69 MPa obtained from full unidirectional Kevlar 49/ Epoxy composites¹¹. In comparison fragmentation tests give values of about 15-20 MPa³ which in fact three times lower than expected.

Fig.5 Interfacial Shear Stress as a function of fibre length normalised to 95% l_t for 1.5% strain (1st loading cycle).

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